

Influence of loopback interference channel in energy harvesting full-duplex relaying network over block rayleigh fading channel: performance analysis

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ABSTRACT

The main idea of this paper is to investigate the system performance (SP) of energy harvesting FD relaying network over block rayleigh fading channel under the influence of the loopback interference channel. In the first stage, we proposed the system model and analyzed the energy harvesting and the information transmission phases. Furthermore, the mathematical form for the outage probability (OP) is analyzed and derived in two kinds of loopback interference: residual self-interference is modeled as AWGN và residual self-interference is still a random variable. All the mathematical, analytical expressions are verified using the Monte Carlo simulation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the last recent years, so many papers focus on the energy harvesting (RH) communication network [1]-[5]. The authors in [6]-[8] proposed and investigated the cooperative wireless networks by a MIMO relay system, the EH process, and how to improve this EH process in them. Furthermore, the multi-user and multi-hop systems and the energy and information transferring at the same time in the communication network is presented in [9]-[11]. The physical layer security problem in the EH communication network and its efficiency is investigated in [12]-[15]. From this literature, we can see that the investigation of the system performance of the EH communication network is necessary to study.

The main idea of this paper is to investigate the system performance (SP) of energy harvesting FD relaying network over block rayleigh fading channel under the influence of the loopback interference channel. In the first stage, we proposed the system model and analyzed the energy harvesting and the information transmission phases. Furthermore, the mathematical form for the outage probability (OP) is analyzed and derived in two kinds of loopback interference: residual self-interference is modeled as AWGN và residual self-interference is still a random variable. All the mathematical, analytical expressions are verified using the Monte Carlo simulation.

2. SYSTEM MODEL

In this paper, the system model is illustrated in Figure 1, and the PSP is drawn in Figure 2. The Energy Harvesting and Information transmission phases can be formulated as (1)-(9) [16]. The received signal at the relay node can be given by (1),

$$y_R = \sqrt{\rho}h_{SR}x_s + h_{RR}x_R + n_R \tag{1}$$

where h_{RR} : residual self-interference channel.

The harvested energy at the relay can be calculated by (2),

$$E_R = \eta(1-\rho)TP_s |h_{SR}|^2 \tag{2}$$

from (2), we have,

$$P_R = \frac{E_R}{T} = \eta(1-\rho)P_s |h_{SR}|^2 = \kappa P_s |h_{SR}|^2 \tag{3}$$

next, the received signal at the destination can be expressed by (4),

$$y_D = h_{RD}x_R + n_D \tag{4}$$

the amplification factor β will be determined as (5),

$$\beta = \frac{x_R}{y_R} = \sqrt{\frac{P_R}{|h_{SR}|^2 P_s + |h_{RR}|^2 P_R + N_0}} \tag{5}$$

from (4) and combining with (5), we can obtain,

$$y_D = h_{RD}\beta y_R + n_D = h_{RD}\beta[\underbrace{\sqrt{\rho}h_{SR}x_s}_{\text{signal}} + \underbrace{h_{RR}x_R}_{\text{interference}} + \underbrace{n_R}_{\text{noise}}] + n_D = \sqrt{\rho}h_{RD}h_{SR}x_s\beta + h_{RD}\beta h_{RR}x_R + h_{RD}\beta n_R + n_D \tag{6}$$

Figure 1. The proposed system

Figure 2. The power splitting phase

after doing some algebra, the SINR can be claimed as (9),

$$\begin{aligned}
 SINR_{AF} &= \frac{E\{|signal|^2\}}{E\{|interference|^2\} + E\{|noise|^2\}} = \frac{\frac{\rho P_s |h_{SR}|^2 |h_{RD}|^2}{|h_{RR}|^2}}{\frac{N_0 P_s |h_{SR}|^2}{P_R |h_{RR}|^2} + P_R |h_{RD}|^2 + \rho N_0} \\
 &= \frac{\rho \kappa \Phi |h_{SR}|^2 |h_{RD}|^2}{\kappa^2 \Phi |h_{SR}|^2 |h_{RD}|^2 |h_{RR}|^2 + \kappa |h_{RR}|^2 + \rho} \tag{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi = \frac{P_s}{N_0}$ and $\kappa = \eta(1 - \rho)$

3. THE SYSTEM PERFORMANCE

Case 1: residual self-interference is still a random variable (RV), the OP of the system at the source destination can be defined as (10),

$$OP_{case1} = \Pr(SINR_{AF} < \gamma_{th}) = \Pr\left(\frac{\rho \kappa \Phi |h_{SR}|^2 |h_{RD}|^2}{\kappa^2 \Phi |h_{SR}|^2 |h_{RD}|^2 |h_{RR}|^2 + \kappa |h_{RR}|^2 + \rho} < \gamma_{th}\right) \tag{10}$$

where $\gamma_{th} = 2^R - 1$ is the threshold of the system and R is the target rate.

Let us denote $X = |h_{SR}|^2 |h_{RD}|^2$ and $Y = |h_{RR}|^2$, the (10) can be rewritten by (11),

$$\begin{aligned}
 OP_{case1} &= \Pr\left(\frac{\rho \kappa \Phi X}{\kappa^2 \Phi XY + \kappa Y + \rho} < \gamma_{th}\right) \\
 &= \begin{cases} \Pr\left(X < \frac{\gamma_{th}(\kappa Y + \rho)}{\rho \kappa \Phi - \kappa^2 \Phi Y \gamma_{th}}\right), Y < \frac{\rho}{\kappa \gamma_{th}} \\ 1, Y \geq \frac{\rho}{\kappa \gamma_{th}} \end{cases} \\
 &= \int_0^{\frac{\rho}{\kappa \gamma_{th}}} F_X\left(\frac{\gamma_{th}(\kappa y + \rho)}{\rho \kappa \Phi - \kappa^2 \Phi y \gamma_{th}}\right) \times f_Y(y) dy + \int_{\frac{\rho}{\kappa \gamma_{th}}}^{\infty} f_Y(y) dy \tag{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

in order to find the probability in (11), we have to calculate the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of X. So, the CDF of X can be found as (12),

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_X(x) &= \Pr(X < x) = \Pr(|h_{SR}|^2 |h_{RD}|^2 < x) = \int_0^{\infty} F_{|h_{SR}|^2}\left(\frac{x}{y} \mid |h_{RD}|^2 = y\right) \times f_{|h_{RD}|^2}(y) dy \\
 &= 1 - \int_0^{\infty} \lambda_{RD} \exp\left(-\frac{\lambda_{SR} x}{y} - \lambda_{RD} y\right) dy \tag{12}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\lambda_{SR}, \lambda_{RD}$ are the mean of RVs $|h_{SR}|^2$ and $|h_{RD}|^2$, respectively.

By applying the (12) [3.324,1] of [17], $F_X(x)$ can be reformulated by,

$$F_X(x) = 1 - 2\sqrt{\lambda_{SR} \lambda_{RD} x} \times K_1\left(2\sqrt{\lambda_{SR} \lambda_{RD} x}\right) \tag{13}$$

where $K_v(\bullet)$ is the modified Bessel function of the second kind and v-th order.

Applying the (13), the OP_{case1} can be rewritten by (14),

$$OP_{case1} = 1 - 2\lambda_{RR} \int_0^{\frac{\rho}{\kappa\gamma_{th}}} \exp(-\lambda_{RR}y) \times \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{SR}\lambda_{RD}\gamma_{th}(\kappa y + \rho)}{\rho\kappa\Phi - \kappa^2\Phi y\gamma_{th}}} \times K_1\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{SR}\lambda_{RD}\gamma_{th}(\kappa y + \rho)}{\rho\kappa\Phi - \kappa^2\Phi y\gamma_{th}}}\right) dy \tag{14}$$

Case 2: residual self-interference is modeled as AWGN with zero mean and variance Ω_{RR} [1].

In this case, from (9), the SINR can be rewritten by,

$$\overline{SINR}_{AF} = \frac{\rho\kappa\Phi|h_{SR}|^2|h_{RD}|^2}{\kappa^2\Phi|h_{SR}|^2|h_{RD}|^2\Omega_{RR} + \kappa\Omega_{RR} + \rho} \tag{15}$$

the OP in case 2 can be calculated as,

$$\begin{aligned} OP_{case2} &= \Pr\left(\overline{SINR}_{AF} < \gamma_{th}\right) = \Pr\left(\frac{\rho\kappa\Phi X}{\kappa^2\Phi X\Omega_{RR} + \kappa\Omega_{RR} + \rho} < \gamma_{th}\right) \\ &= \Pr\left(X\left[\rho\kappa\Phi - \kappa^2\Phi\Omega_{RR}\gamma_{th}\right] < \gamma_{th}\left[\kappa\Omega_{RR} + \rho\right]\right) \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

so that probability in (16) is available. It means that our system can be operated, we must estimate Ω_{RR} , so that satisfy the condition: $\Omega_{RR} < \frac{\rho}{\kappa\gamma_{th}}$ [18-21].

Hence, the OP_{case2} can be claimed by applying result from (13),

$$\begin{aligned} OP_{case2} &= \Pr\left(X < \frac{\gamma_{th}\left[\kappa\Omega_{RR} + \rho\right]}{\rho\kappa\Phi - \kappa^2\Phi\Omega_{RR}\gamma_{th}}\right) \\ &= 1 - 2\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{SR}\lambda_{RD}\gamma_{th}(\kappa\Omega_{RR} + \rho)}{\rho\kappa\Phi - \kappa^2\Phi\Omega_{RR}\gamma_{th}}} \times K_1\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{SR}\lambda_{RD}\gamma_{th}(\kappa\Omega_{RR} + \rho)}{\rho\kappa\Phi - \kappa^2\Phi\Omega_{RR}\gamma_{th}}}\right) \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As in [22]-[25], we use the Monte Carlo simulation for convincing the correctness of the analytical section. The influence of ψ and ρ on the system performance in terms of OP is shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4, respectively. In Figure 3, the main system parameters are set as $R=1$ bps/Hz, $\rho=0.85$, $\eta=1$. As a result, the system OP has a massive fall with increasing of Φ from -5dB to 20dB in both cases. Similarly, the system OP has a massive increase with rising of ρ from 0 to 1. In Figure 4, we set the primary system parameters as $R=1$ bps, $\Phi=5$ dB, $\eta=1, 0.5$, and $\Omega_{RR}=0$ and 0.05 dB for both cases. In Figure 4 and Figure 5, the simulation and analytical value are the same for convincing the analytical section.

Figure 3. OP versus ψ

Figure 4. OP versus ρ

Figure 4 shows the OP versus ρ . Furthermore, the system OP as the function of η , while η varies from 0 to 1 is illustrated in Figure 5. In this figure, the system parameters are set as $R=1$ bps, $\Phi=5$ dB, $\rho=0.25$, 0.85 , and $\Omega_{RR}=0.25$ and 2.5 dB for both cases. The system OP falls with the rising of η . On the other hand, the system OP as the function of R when R increases from 0 to 6bps/Hz is shown in Figure 6 with the main system parameters as $\rho=0.5$, $\Phi=7$ dB, $\eta=1$ and $\Omega_{RR}=0$ dB. As shown in Figure 6, the system OP has a rise with R . In both Figure 5 and Figure 6, the simulation curves overlap the analytical curves to verify the mathematical section's correctness.

Figure 6. OP versus R

5. CONCLUSION

The main idea of this paper is investigated the system performance of energy harvesting FD relaying network over block rayleigh fading channel under the influence of the loopback interference channel. In the first stage, we proposed the system model and analyzed the energy harvesting and the information transmission phases. Furthermore, the mathematical form for the outage probability (OP) is analyzed and derived in two kinds of loopback interference: residual self-interference is modeled as AWGN và residual self-interference is still a random variable. All the mathematical, analytical expressions are verified using the Monte Carlo simulation.

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